

Thermal virtual sensing for electronic components and systems: exploring the robustness of Kalman filtering

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Abstract

Digital Twins (DTs) of Electronic Components and Systems (ECS) can be used for thermal analysis and design optimization. However, one of the main difficulties is identifying the physical parameters of the numerical model underlying the DT. Indeed, these parameters can vary across devices and even during their lifecycle. A methodology that can accommodate for uncertainties is therefore desired. This work presents a Kalman Filter (KF)-based approach employing a Reduced Order Model (ROM) of a considered ECS. The robustness of the KF with respect to uncertain parameter values is investigated by evaluating its capability to correctly estimate the ECS thermal state while relying on a model with perturbed parameter values or boundary conditions. Evaluation of the KF performance regarding dealing with parameter uncertainties indicate the effectiveness of the proposed approach.

1 Introduction

Electronic Systems and components (ECS), e.g., PCBs, packages, and chips, are massively present in our daily lives from electronic devices, to mobility, home appliances, IoT, power electronics and so on. These systems are subject to failures and the majority of them are caused by thermal issues, according to [1]. Insufficient thermal management may be the cause of this lack of reliability, in cascade, lowering the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of this kind of systems and increasing e-waste [2]. To improve thermal management, thermal measurements at critical locations, e.g., solder joints, would be helpful but they are often inaccessible. Therefore, to tackle this challenge, solutions were investigated to obtain their estimates exploiting offline simulations of models, e.g., RC lumped thermal models [3, 4] or finite element-based models [5]. These models revealed to be helpful in system designing and cooling strategies optimization [6], but, because of manufacturing and working condition uncertainties, they may significantly differ from the real system and cannot be used out-of-the-box to estimate temperatures in operation at inaccessible locations. They need to be characterised [7] for every system iteration and even after being characterized, it is possible that the model is no longer representative of the true thermal behaviour of the systems. In fact, their parameters could have changed because of a number of factors like ageing, dust, clogging, working operation, and so on.

Temperature estimation therefore needs to be corrected by leveraging mathematical tools that work by mixing

information coming from models and from physical real-time measurements. One of the approaches is the Kalman filtering [8, 9] that is a linear optimal state estimator that works by comparing the output generated by a mathematical model with measurement data to produce estimates of unknown variables. Exploiting the observability property of linear systems [9], virtual sensors can be enabled for structural dynamics [10, 11] and vibro-acoustic [12] applications. That is, while using a reduced number of sensors, measuring part of the field one wants to know, the system state can be estimated and exploited to compute the remainder of the field.

In the analysed case, the ECS model employed in the Kalman Filter (KF) can be a lumped thermal network [13] or a more detailed numerical model [14]. The latter is characterized by a higher level of detail, and is therefore desired. Unfortunately, its real-time execution is often unfeasible because of computational cost. To overcome this obstacle, Reduced Order Models (ROMs) [15, 16] have been generated starting from complex full order numerical models. Not only do they enable real-time execution thanks to computational reduction, but, in the field of electronics, ROMs are also employed in the KF.

Our aim is to investigate the robustness capability of this approach in rejecting processing errors generated by uncertainties in a considered model. Indeed, the robustness of this methodology in the considered setting has not been explored in depth yet, to our knowledge, and is of utmost importance given the number of uncertainties present in ECS thermal analysis.

The methodology is described in Section 2 focusing on the two ingredients: the ROM and the KF. A use case is described and analysed in Section 3 where several sensor configurations are tested to highlight strengths and criticalities of the approach. Lastly, in Section 4 the main findings are summarized and future developments are discussed.

2 Methodology

The proposed approach considers a KF employing a ROM of a highly detailed ECS numerical model. In particular, the Finite Volume Method is applied to an ECS model to generate its full order model (FOM). A reduction tool is used on the FOM to obtain a ROM, that allows for real-time execution.

2.1 The Reduced Order Model

The ROM used in this work is exported from Simcenter Flotherm [17], an electronic cooling simulation software solution for electronics thermal analysis. Among its functionalities, it is capable of exporting a ROM of a linear thermal conduction model of an ECS. It leverages an enhanced multi-point moment matching algorithm, introduced in [18], applied to a FOM to generate a ROM. The model comes with input vector $S \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i}$ (n_i is the number of inputs) for the dissipated powers, output vector $T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_o}$ (n_o is the number of outputs) for the temperature field, and the state vector $T_r \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (n is the number of state variables) for the reduced temperature field. The model is a first-order system defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} M_r \dot{T}_r + K_r T_r &= L_r S + S_r^{amb}, \\ T &= V T_r, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where M_r , K_r , and L_r are the reduced thermal mass matrix, the reduced thermal stiffness matrix, and reduced source matrix. The temperature fields T and T_r are linked by the projection matrix V . The reduced ambient source vector S_r^{amb} , depending on the assigned boundary conditions, represents the ambient heat entering the system.

In order to be employed in the KF, the model in (1) must be first rewritten in a state-space formulation, that is

$$\begin{aligned} \underbrace{\dot{T}}_{\dot{x}} &= \underbrace{(-M_r^{-1} K_r) T_r}_{Ax} + \underbrace{(M_r^{-1} L_r) S}_{Bu} + \underbrace{M_r^{-1} S_r^{amb}}_d, \\ \underbrace{T}_{y} &= \underbrace{V T_r}_{Cx}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where x , u , d , and y are respectively the state vector, the input vector, the constant load vector, and the output vector, while A , B , and C , are the state matrix, the input matrix, and the output matrix.

2.2 The Kalman Filter

Since thermal measurements are discrete, a discrete-time KF is adopted. The model in (2) is discretized using an exponential time integration scheme (see [19]). Stochastic noise terms are added so to have a stochastic deterministic system formulation

$$\begin{aligned}x_{t+1} &= A_d x_t + B_d u_t + d_d + w, \\y_t &= C_d x_t + v.\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

where the subscript ' t ' indicates a quantity corresponding to the time instant t . In particular, while x_t and y_t are computed by simulating the model, u_t and d_d can be known a-priori, estimated (or measured) with other methods or calculated by forward simulations of other models.

The KF is a linear optimal state estimator that generates a Gaussian state estimate $\mathcal{N}(\hat{x}_t^+, P_t^+)$, with \hat{x}_t^+ the estimated state and P_t^+ the state estimate covariance matrix, and is optimal in minimizing the trace of P_t^+ . It accommodates for process noises w and measurement noises v by adding them in (3) and assuming $w \sim \mathcal{N}(0, Q)$ and $v \sim \mathcal{N}(0, R)$ with Q and R respectively the process noise and the measurement noise covariance matrices, that are tuning parameters of the KF.

The KF algorithm is characterized by two iterative steps being the prediction step and the update (or correction) step. For the considered model, the first is represented by

$$\hat{x}_{t+1}^- = A_d \hat{x}_t^+ + B_d u_t + d_d, \quad (4a)$$

$$\hat{y}_{t+1}^- = C_d \hat{x}_{t+1}^-, \quad (4b)$$

$$P_{t+1}^- = A_d P_t^+ A_d^\top + Q, \quad (4c)$$

and the latter is represented by

$$K_{t+1} = P_{t+1}^- C_d^\top [C_d P_{t+1}^- C_d^\top + R]^{-1}, \quad (5a)$$

$$\hat{x}_{t+1}^+ = \hat{x}_{t+1}^- + K_{t+1} (\tilde{y}_{t+1} - \hat{y}_{t+1}^-), \quad (5b)$$

$$P_{t+1}^+ = [I - K_{t+1} C_d] P_{t+1}^-. \quad (5c)$$

Notice that the superscripts '-' and '+' respectively indicate quantities before and after being corrected. The vectors \hat{y} and \tilde{y} respectively represent the estimated and the measured outputs. Equations (4a) and (4b) directly stem from (3) and describe the predictions of \hat{x} and \hat{y} . The prediction of P is described by (4c). Equation (5a) is to calculate the Kalman Gain; the higher the values in K , the higher the KF correction. Equations (5b) and (5c) represent the corrections of \hat{x} and \hat{P} .

3 Robustness analysis

To demonstrate the capabilities of the approach, a test board has been designed and studied in a simulated environment. After generating the model and simulating measurement data, the proposed approach is tested with models characterized by a perturbation of a modelling parameter, the peripheral Heat Transfer Coefficient (HTC), to simulate a modelling uncertainty. The robustness of the KF in estimating temperatures in inaccessible locations is evaluated by comparing its estimations with simulated reference data.

3.1 Use case setup

The considered setup consists of a test PCBA (printed circuit board assembly), i.e., a board with assembled components. The board dimensions are $38mm \times 16mm \times 1.6mm$ and it is made of *FR4* dielectric (Flame

Retardant 4), *copper* circuitry, pins, and thermal vias. The circuitry, on the top of the board, is unknown. Therefore, a top layer material *TL* is considered for the top $35\mu\text{m}$ of the board with thermal properties chosen based on the assumed copper concentration in the layer, that is 10%. The six pins on the left side of the board (see Fig. 1) have dimensions $4\text{mm} \times 2\text{mm} \times 1.6\text{mm}$ each. The thermal vias are installed below the die-attaches of components 3 and 5. In particular, they are characterized by a 3×3 grid, with 1mm pitch in both directions and each hole is 0.5mm of diameter and $25\mu\text{m}$ of plating thickness. In this model they are simplified by cuboids made of a thermal material *TV* having equivalent thermal properties.

Figure 1: Top view of the test board with numbered components.

There are six components mounted on top of the board (see Fig. 1) consisting of *silicon* chips glued to the board by means of common *glue* die-attaches. Chips dimensions are $3\text{mm} \times 3\text{mm} \times 0.4\text{mm}$ for five of them and $6\text{mm} \times 6\text{mm} \times 0.4\text{mm}$ for the remaining one. The die-attaches cover the whole bottom area of the chips and are $40\mu\text{m}$ thick. The components are connected to the circuitry through wire bonds that are, however, negligible from the thermal point of view and are therefore not modelled.

Table 1: Thermal material properties of the system.

Material	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]		Density [kg/m^3]	Specific heat [J/kgK]
	Through-Plane	Normal		
FR4	0.3	0.3	1200	880
Silicon	100	100	2330	700
Glue	0.5	0.5	2000	1000
Copper	385	385	8930	385
TV	0.35	20.9	1340.7	702.9
TL	38.77	38.77	1973	830.5

The thermal properties of the mentioned materials are reported in Table 1. Notice that the thermal conductivity of the silicon is fixed although it is well known that it is non-linearly dependent on temperature [20]. This simplification was necessary for the ROM export and is not, however, a source of large error in the considered scenario thanks to its high thermal conductivity. It should be furthermore noticed that the only material with different plane and normal thermal conductivities is TV. This is because of the thermal via geometry which guides the heat down through the board.

A 35°C ambient temperature is assumed. The system is laying on a cooling plate (represented by a peripheral HTC of $2000W/m^2K$) on the bottom while it is cooled by natural air convection (peripheral HTC of $10W/m^2K$) on the remaining surfaces.

In the considered scenario, the small size chips dissipate $0.4W$ each while the large size chip dissipates $1.2W$. These inputs have been chosen to make the chips reach steady state temperatures of around 100°C , common for this kind of setup. The inputs are step functions that turn the power dissipation on at $t = 0s$ and are assumed to be known a-priori. The system is at rest before the inputs are turned on, that is, the whole temperature field is at ambient temperature.

Figure 2: Locations of embedded sensors and board sensors.

The system comes with a thermal *embedded sensor* (ES) per component measuring the corresponding junction temperature in the centroid of the chip plus two additional thermal *board sensors* (BS) on the top of the board as in Fig. 2. Their locations were chosen to minimize the location sensitivity associated to spatial location errors, that is by locating them where the spatial planar temperature field gradient at steady state is low. The *virtual sensors* (VS) are in the centroid of each die-attach as in Fig. 3. This is a location of interest where thermal stresses may lead to a failure but where temperature is not measured because of inaccessibility. ES # and VS # indicate ES and VS placed in component #.

Figure 3: Locations of virtual sensors.

The KF is initialized assuming the ambient temperature is known a-priori, so \hat{x}_0^+ is set accordingly, and $P_0^+ = 100 \cdot I$. The measurement noise of each temperature probe is assumed to be $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_R)$ with $\sigma_R = 0.1$, although no measurement noise is added to the simulated data, for the sake of clarity in the results. While R can be obtained exploiting the a-priori knowledge of the measurement noise as $R = \sigma_R^2 \cdot I_{n_o}$, it is more challenging to tune Q . This describes the error between the numerical model and the physical system, which, in turn, depends on the level of detail of the model, uncertainty of the parameters, and time sampling. The tuning of Q normally depends on the skills of experts and their knowledge of the specific field. In this case, like it is often the case, Q is assumed to be diagonal with equal variances. The L-curve method, described in [11], has been adopted to find a suitable value, leading to: $Q = \sigma_Q^2 \cdot I_n = 0.01 \cdot I_n$.

3.2 Numerical results

The bottom HTC is selected for the robustness analysis of the proposed approach. This is a parameter that can be estimated but is intrinsically uncertain [21]. Moreover, it is the parameter on which the thermal behaviour of the considered system depends the most, that is, its variation can significantly influence the entire system temperature field.

For this purpose, three different ROMs have been generated. The first is the unperturbed model with nominal parameter values reported in Sec. 3.1, simulated to generate temperature data at the locations of the sensors. The others are perturbed models, used for virtual sensing. The perturbed models differ from the unperturbed one for the bottom HTC value. One is with a bottom HTC of $1000W/m^2K$, that is -50% compared to the unperturbed one, and the other is with a bottom HTC of $3000W/m^2K$, that is $+50\%$ compared to the unperturbed one. We purposefully select large variations of the bottom HTC value to test the limits of the approach although the uncertainty for this kind of parameter is typically lower [21].

Since variations of HTC values do not affect the transient behaviour of this system, we focus on steady state temperatures. We do this by launching simulations with a time span long enough to reach steady state. Temperatures at the last time step T are considered to be at steady state. For each i -th sensor, we define the error $\epsilon_i(T)$ (in $^{\circ}C$) and the percentage error $\delta_i(T)$

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_i(T) &= \hat{y}_i^+(T) - \tilde{y}_i(T), \\ \delta_i(T) &= 100 \cdot \left| \frac{\epsilon_i(T)}{\tilde{y}_i(T)} \right|,\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

where \hat{y}_i^+ and \tilde{y}_i indicate its estimated temperature after correction and the corresponding temperature data. The performance of virtual sensing is assessed by observing errors at the virtual sensor locations. The KF employing the two perturbed models is compared to the baseline of the FS of those same perturbed models, i.e. without KF correction. In particular, the KF is fed with temperature data from embedded and board sensors. Specifically, we will study different scenarios using different sensor configurations. In the first case all embedded sensors will be employed. However, this corresponds to an ideal case and, in realistic scenarios, thermal sensors are not installed in every component. Therefore, the robustness of the approach is assessed with respect to different sensor configurations with reduced numbers of sensors and/or different locations. The tested sensor configurations are described in Table 2.

Table 2: Tested sensor configurations with KF.

Sensor configuration	Sensors employed in the KF
1 st	All embedded sensors
2 nd	ES 2
3 rd	BS 1
4 th	BS 1 and BS 2
5 th	ES 3, ES 5, BS 1, and BS 2

Virtual sensing by Forward Simulation

The virtual sensing steady state errors of the FS are reported in Table 3. In general, HTC underestimation led to higher errors compared to the HTC overestimation case. VS 1, VS 2, VS 4, and VS 6, without thermal vias underneath, are the best performing virtual sensors although they can still experience large errors ranging from VS 6 with $\delta = -1\%$ in the $+50\%HTC$ case to VS 2 with $\delta = 6.7\%$ in the $-50\%HTC$ case. By contrast, VS 3 and VS 5, with thermal vias underneath, are the worst performing virtual sensors, reaching more than 17% error in the $-50\%HTC$ case and more than 8% error in the $+50\%HTC$ case. The cause of this difference resides in the total thermal resistance from component to the bottom surface of the board. It is lower for components with thermal vias underneath compared to others because of the high normal thermal conductivity of TV (see Table 1). Therefore, by varying the bottom HTC, the thermal resistances from components 3 and 5 and the bottom of the board will be altered more compared to those for other components, and these variations reflect on the virtual sensors.

Table 3: Virtual sensing steady state errors with estimates from FS.

HTC	VS 1		VS 2		VS 3		VS 4		VS 5		VS 6	
	ϵ	δ										
-50%	4.4	4.5%	6.6	6.7%	11.4	17.6%	6.1	6.7%	11.4	17.6%	3	3%
+50%	-1.7	1.8%	-2.8	2.9%	-5.5	8.5%	-2.6	2.9%	-5.5	8.5%	-1	1.0%

Virtual sensing by Kalman filtering (1st sensor configuration)

The transient results of the KF with the 1st sensor configuration (see Table 2) are shown in Fig. 4, and steady state errors are highlighted in Table 4. At steady state, all virtual sensors without thermal vias underneath them, that are VS 1, VS 2, VS 4, and VS 6, experience errors lower than 0.1%, while VS 3 and VS 5 reach 1.5% error in the -50% HTC case, that is less than a fourth of errors in FS (see Table 3). The methodology almost completely rejects the modelling uncertainty in all virtual sensors. However, as already stated, the tested sensor configuration is ideal, while in a more realistic scenario only one embedded sensor is available.

Figure 4: Virtual sensors transient simulations, KF with 1st sensor configuration. Reference is from data.

Table 4: Virtual sensors steady state errors with estimates from KF, 1st sensor configuration.

HTC	VS 1		VS 2		VS 3		VS 4		VS 5		VS 6	
	ϵ	δ										
-50%	0.02	0.02%	0.04	0.04%	1	1.5%	0.02	0.02%	1.0	1.6%	0.05	0.05%
+50%	-0.03	0.03%	-0.02	0.02%	-0.8	1.3%	-0.03	0.04%	-0.8	1.3%	0.01	0.01%

Virtual sensing by Kalman filtering (2nd sensor configuration)

The transient results of the KF with the 2nd sensor configuration (employing ES 2 only, see Table 2) are shown in Fig. 5, and steady state errors are highlighted in Table 5. VS 3, VS 4, VS 5, and VS 6 now perform like in FS (see Table 3) with light correction, while VS 2, which is very close to ES 2, performs almost the same as in the previous sensor configuration (see Table 4). VS 1 shows very good performance with errors lower than 1%, even without having a sensor in its component. VS 3 performs much worse than VS 1, although equally distant from ES 2. This different performance is explained by the weak thermal coupling of components with thermal vias underneath to the surrounding others. Indeed, because of the high normal thermal conductivity of TV (see Table 1), the heat generated in component 3 is directed to the bottom of the board for the most. Consequently, the temperature in ES 2 is weakly related to the temperature in component 3 while is highly related to the temperature in component 1. The KF correction performance depends on the thermal coupling present in the system, as this allows to correct the full system state using a limited set of physical measurements. The performance decrease in VS 4 and VS 6 suggests that they are too far from ES 2, given the uncoupled nature of the considered system. In all, performance has decreased as expected, but the uncertainty rejection in VS 1 highlighted the virtual sensing capability of the methodology. This can give an indication of the next sensor configuration to improve the results by using a properly located board sensor. Indeed, a sensor on the board could be placed closer to VS 4, to improve its temperature estimates, without going too far from VS 1 and VS 2, so to keep their similar performance. This is studied in the next sensor configuration.

Figure 5: Virtual sensors transient simulations, KF with 2nd sensor configuration. Reference is from data.

Table 5: Virtual sensors steady state errors with estimates from KF, 2nd sensor configuration.

HTC	VS 1		VS 2		VS 3		VS 4		VS 5		VS 6	
	ϵ	δ										
-50%	0.5	0.6%	0.05	0.05%	9.0	14%	4.5	5%	10.4	16.0%	3	3%
+50%	-0.1	0.1%	-0.02	0.02%	-4.9	7.6%	-2.1	2.3%	-5.3	8.1%	-1.0	1.0%

Virtual sensing by Kalman filtering (3rd sensor configuration)

The transient results of the KF with the 3rd sensor configuration (employing BS 1 only, see Table 2) are shown in Fig. 6, and steady state errors are highlighted in Table 6. This configuration revealed to be effective, as desired, with VS 1, VS 2, and VS 4 experiencing less than 1% error thanks to the vicinity to BS 1. By contrast, only minor improvements can be noticed in VS 3, VS 5, and VS 6 by comparing Tabs. 5 and 6. Even though BS 1 was not enough to improve satisfactorily VS 3 and VS 5 performance, it actually worked for all other surrounding virtual sensors. It highlighted the capabilities of board sensors within this methodology. Therefore, an additional board sensor can improve performance in VS 6.

Figure 6: Virtual sensors transient simulations, KF with 3rd sensor configuration. Reference is from data.

Table 6: Virtual sensors steady state errors with estimates from KF, 3rd sensor configuration.

HTC	VS 1		VS 2		VS 3		VS 4		VS 5		VS 6	
	ϵ	δ										
-50%	-0.2	0.2%	0.3	0.3%	8.6	13.3%	0.8	0.8%	7.8	11.9%	2.9	2.9%
+50%	0.5	0.5%	0.2	0.2%	-4.8	7.4%	-0.3	0.3%	-4.5	6.9%	-1.0	1.0%

Virtual sensing by Kalman filtering (4th sensor configuration)

VS 6 transient results of the KF with the 4th sensor configuration (employing BS 1 and BS 2, see Table 2) are shown in Fig. 7. The other virtual sensors are not reported here as they perform very similarly to the previous configuration (see Fig. 6). Steady state errors are highlighted in Table 7. This configuration finally moves the estimated temperatures of VS 6 towards the reference thanks to BS 2. The VS 6 estimation error, for the -50%HTC case, is 2/3 of the FS corresponding error (see Table 3), and is lower than 1% in the +50%HTC case.

Figure 7: VS 6 transient simulation, KF with 4th sensors configuration. Reference is from data.

Table 7: Virtual sensors steady state errors with estimates from KF, 4th sensor configuration.

HTC	VS 1		VS 2		VS 3		VS 4		VS 5		VS 6	
	ϵ	δ										
-50%	-0.09	0.1%	0.5	0.5%	8.7	13.4%	0.2	0.3%	7.4	11.4%	2.0	2.0%
+50%	0.5	0.5%	0.1	0.1%	-4.8	7.4%	-0.1	0.1%	-4.4	6.8%	-0.8	0.8%

Virtual sensing by Kalman filtering (5th sensor configuration)

The results of the previous sensor configurations show that board sensors can be employed to estimate temperatures at virtual sensors without thermal vias underneath. However, they are not effective for the remaining virtual sensors, with thermal vias underneath, because of the weak thermal coupling issue highlighted by the different performance between VS 1 and VS 3 in the KF with the 2nd sensor configuration. Therefore, to meet performance comparable to the ideal case, investigated in the 1st sensor configuration, the embedded sensors ES 3 and ES 5 are necessary. This 5th, and final, configuration is analysed here, with steady state errors highlighted in Table 8. As expected, VS 1, VS 2, VS 4, and VS 6 perform like the previous configuration (with BS 1 and BS 2), while VS 3 and VS 5 perform like the 1st sensor configuration (see Fig. 4 and Table 4) because of the dedicated embedded sensors ES 3 and ES 5.

Table 8: Virtual sensors steady state errors with estimates from KF, 5th sensor configuration.

HTC	VS 1		VS 2		VS 3		VS 4		VS 5		VS 6	
	ϵ	δ										
-50%	0.2	0.2%	0.3	0.4%	1	1.5%	-0.1	0.2%	1	1.5%	1.9	2.0%
+50%	-0.4	0.4%	0.01	0.02%	-0.8	1.3%	0.2	0.2%	-0.8	1.3%	-0.8	0.8%

Sensor configurations comparison

The *relative residual norm* of virtual sensors at each time step t

$$RRN(t) = \frac{\|\epsilon(t)\|}{\|\tilde{y}(t)\|} \quad (7)$$

is shown for all sensor configurations in Fig. 8 to summarize and close this section. They show the loss of uncertainty rejection passing from the 1st to the 2nd configuration and the drop of the relative residual norm with the following configurations, highlighting the effectiveness of the proposed approach by using board

sensors, e.g. BS 1 and BS 2, and of embedded sensors in the components with thermal vias underneath, e.g. ES 3 and ES 5. Similar performance can be observed by comparing the KF with the 1st configuration, where RRN at steady state is below 0.01 in both cases, to the KF with the 5th configuration, where RRN at steady state is below 0.02 in both cases, while RRN in FS at steady state is almost 0.1 in the $-50\%HTC$ case.

Figure 8: RRN for KF simulations with every sensor configuration compared to RRN for FS.

4 Conclusion

The approach proposed in this work consists of employing a ROM of a thermal DT of an ECS in a KF provided with measurements from a reduced number of sensors to obtain real-time thermal measurements from virtual sensors, i.e., estimated temperatures of the full temperature field. However, the parameter values adopted in the model are generally uncertain, possibly leading to estimation errors. The robustness of the methodology has been investigated by considering a $\pm 50\%$ variation of the bottom HTC value of the considered system. The performance was assessed, in a simulation environment, by observing the temperature estimation errors of virtual sensors in the die-attaches. Several sensor configurations, consisting of combinations of embedded sensors and board sensors, have been explored. The ideal scenario with an embedded sensor per component revealed to be effective in solving the problem with the maximum estimation error being 1%. It was noticed that embedded sensors and board sensors, thanks to the proposed approach, allow to correctly estimate the temperature in surrounding virtual sensors in the case of good thermal coupling. Therefore, the amount of necessary embedded sensors in the system can be reduced. Unfortunately, virtual sensor temperatures were challenging to estimate without dedicated embedded sensors in case of weak thermal coupling. This is particularly the case for the components with thermal vias, which direct most of the heat to the bottom of the board. As a consequence, temperatures for those components are not highly correlated to temperature rises in the surrounding, where a sensor might be, and the KF is not able to correct them. Embedded sensors were necessary for those cases. Overall, the presented methodology highlighted

the robustness of the KF in solving the virtual sensing problem and showed the capability of reducing the number of sensors needed without significant performance loss.

This work also highlights the critical question of the number and locations of sensors with respect to the performance of virtual sensing. In this case, additional board sensor locations have been suggested by observing the surface thermal gradient at steady state of the system. Furthermore, the issue in estimating the temperatures of virtual sensors with thermal vias underneath forced us to use the embedded sensors above them. However, no proof of optimality of the selected sensor locations was given. Future studies will assess the problem of Optimal Sensors Placement [22] to further improve the approach capabilities.

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